

**Multispiral Computed Tomography Comparative Analysis and Justification
of Chronic Lung Disease Complications in Patients with Covid-19 Pneumonia**

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Due to the high mortality from COVID-19 pneumonia, adequate and timely diagnosis comes to the fore. At the same time, radiation research methods play a huge role in identifying signs of inflammatory changes in the lungs, determining the volume of lung damage, monitoring treatment and predicting the course of the disease. The most informative method of detecting changes in the lungs associated with COVID-19 is rightfully computed tomography of the thoracic cavity, which allows identifying typical manifestations of viral lung lesions [1,7]. However, in some cases, CT is problematic, especially in patients in the intensive care unit. In addition, due to the high radiation load, the question arises of limiting the use of this method in the framework of frequent control studies.

The purpose of the investigation. In order to reduce radiation exposure and obtain additional diagnostic information, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was used in a number of patients [8].

Radiography is significantly inferior in the sensitivity of computed tomography, it allows us to confidently detect only severe forms of pneumonia [6]. Most of the available studies indicate that traditional lung radiography has low sensitivity at an early stage. Ultrasound examination (ultrasound) of the lungs is considered as an alternative to X- ray studies [2]. Important advantages of ultrasound compared to

radiography are: zero radiation load, assessment of infiltration in Live mode, the ability to monitor the dynamics of pneumonia. [3]. Demonstrating high sensitivity in the diagnosis of pneumonia, ultrasound at the same time has its limitations — sensitivity parameters are significantly reduced with a small lesion of lung tissue, localization of pneumonia in areas difficult to reach for the ultrasound wave [3, 5]. In this regard, ultrasound in the diagnosis of coronavirus pneumonia requires a more detailed study.

Materials and methods

The clinical and radiation data of 27 patients (15 women and 12 men) who underwent COVID-19 and were observed in medical and preventive institutions of the city of Karaganda, Temirtau from August 2020 to December 2021 were analyzed. The average age of patients was 37.2 ± 15.7 years. All patients underwent high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT), which was performed with a thin slice of 1-2 mm at the inhalation delay in the pulmonary and mediastinal modes with a scanning area from the tops of the lungs to the sinuses, in the native mode on devices with 128 slices. Scanning was carried out on a GE Optima CT 660 computed tomograph

The consequence of the high density of recording for CT studies, as well as the temporary technical malfunction of CT machines caused by the increased round-the-clock load on X-ray tubes, was the inability to perform CT in some patients. It is in such a situation of lack of opportunities that magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has become an alternative method of diagnosing pulmonary changes.

MRI examination of the chest organs was carried out in 9 patients on Toshiba Titan Vantage 1.5 T MRI scanners (Canon Medical), in T1-, T2-weighted modes (T1VI, T2VI), STIR-modes, in axial and frontal planes, with breath retention.

Radiography was performed in straight posterior and lateral projections, when the patient's condition allowed him to be in a vertical position, whereas in a straight anterior projection — with the patient's horizontal position. During X-ray examination, pneumonia was confirmed or excluded, the extent of darkening was estimated depending on the localization by segments, the presence of complications in the form of destructive processes, pleural effusion.

Ultrasound examination of the lungs was performed on a Toshiba AplioMX ultrasound machine using a 5 MHz convexic sensor.

Ultrasound assessed the localization of the process, the length of the infiltration site, as well as the number of B-lines and "air bronchograms" per unit area.

Radiation diagnostic methods were used strictly according to the indications and prescription of the attending physician, and patients or their legal representatives signed an informed consent to conduct the study. Results and discussion. Computed tomography.

References

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